

DEFORMATION EVALUATION OF ELASTIC COMPOSITE BLADE MODELS FOR A TIDAL POWER GENERATION BY FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION ANALYSIS

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1 Introduction

Generally, renewable energy sources are favorable for the environment compared with conventional energy sources. Wind energy and solar energy are the representatives for the renewable energy sources. However, it is difficult to generate power stably from them because they are largely influenced by climate conditions. On the other hand, tidal energy can be a predictable energy source because tidal currents depend on the stable forces such as centrifugal forces created by the earth rotation and the gravitational pull of the moon and the earth [1]. Such an advantage also belongs to the ocean current. There are two representative ways to convert the tidal energy to the electric energy. One way is to utilize a range of the tide. Reserved water in a tidal barrage rotates a turbine and generates electricity in a similar way with run-of-river hydro power plants. Another way is to extract the kinetic energy from marine currents. Free flowing water rotates the undersea turbine and generates electricity in a similar way with wind power generation. The latter way is considered to be better for the environment than the former one [2]. Our studies focus on the electricity generation method using free flowing water and a turbine.

In the turbine for a generation system, pitch control systems are generally needed to stabilize generating power of electricity and prevent overloads of the turbine blade. This system changes the pitch angle of the blade in order to reduce or increase the cross-sectional area toward flow direction in accordance with the current speed. One of the pitch control methods is active pitch control, which mechanically adjust the angle using the motor control system [3]. Marine Current

Turbine LTD. has developed the tidal turbine with the active pitch control by which the generation system can be used in both the current directions due to the tide [4]. Alternatively, passive pitch control can be available. In this case, structural and material properties are designed or arranged so that the appropriate bending and twisting deformation of the blade occurs by forces including fluid forces and centrifugal forces. It does not require the motor control system which results in the higher initial and maintenance costs. Yanagihara et al. have proposed the passive pitch control in wind turbine blades [5]. They aimed to change the pitch angle by twisting the composite root based on the effect of a cross-elasticity using centrifugal forces. Finally, they concluded that it is difficult to utilize passive pitch control systems for wind turbine blades because aerodynamic forces are too small to deform sufficiently. However, since the density of water is about 800 times as that of air and the rotor diameter of a tidal turbine is generally less than that of a wind turbine, fluid forces might be available for passive pitch control.

We should evaluate the performance of a turbine blade deformed according to the current and rotation speed in order to design the passive pitch control blades. Fluid and structural behaviors should be considered not individually but as a fluid-structure interaction problem because the influence of the deformation on the fluid can't be neglected [6]. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) can be used to calculate the fluid force of various types of turbine blades in diverse environments and finite element analysis (FEA) can be also employed to determine the deformation and assess the strength. The

interaction analysis might be validated by compared with experiments.

The light weight and extreme strength are essential to the tidal turbine blade [7]. In this study, two types of composite turbine blade models were used to investigate the passive pitch control. The diameter of the two models was 1 m. The preliminary investigation had been conducted with the blades of 0.25 m in diameter [8]. One model (Model1) was assembled with several parts. A spar and skins were made of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). Epoxy resin as core was used to form the blade body. Model1 has lower stiffness in torsion so that the blade would cause torsional deformation and feather as the current speed was increasing. The other model (Model2) was laminated with CFRP. Model2 has higher stiffness in torsion. We compared two models in order to confirm the effect of the passive pitch control.

Deformation, namely the deflection in the current direction and the torsion, in the diverse current and rotation speed was calculated by a fluid-structure interaction analysis (FSIA) with CFD and FEA. Then the calculated results were compared with those of experiments which were implemented in a towing tank. The finite element (FE) model of the blade was also validated by static load tests. Consequently, we confirmed that FSIA used in this study can be used to evaluate the performance of the tidal turbine with passive pitch control and to design the optimal one.

2 Deformation Evaluation of Composite Blade Model

2.1 Passive Pitch Control Blade

It is required for a tidal power generation to stabilize generated power under a certain range of current speed. In the case of active pitch control, the motor control system placed at the root of the blade changes the pitch angles of blade from root to tip as shown in Fig.1 (a). When the output power is going to exceed the rated power, the motor control system turns the blade so that the attack angles decrease. Eventually, the rotation speed remains constant, and output power is stabilized at the rated power. On the other hand, in the case of passive pitch control proposed in this study, the structure and materials of the blade are designed or arranged so that the blade itself bend and twist only by fluid forces. As the

flow speed increases, the attack angles gradually decrease along the blade as shown in Fig.1 (b). In the result, it is expected that the output power would be stabilized. This function can be realized by utilizing special properties of composite materials [9]: larger allowable deformation and tailorable elastic property by using anisotropy. A performance curve expected by the passive pitch control is shown in Fig.2 and the output power approaches to the rated power as current speed increases.

Fig.1. Concepts of active pitch control and passive pitch control.

Fig.2. Expected performance curve of passive pitch control.

2.2 Composite Blade Model

Validation of FSIA and the tank tests were implemented with reduced-size blade models by comparing the results of analyses and experiments. We made two pieces of blade models to form 1-meter turbine. The CAD model with dimensions is shown in Fig.3. The airfoil is NACA4409.

We manufactured two types of experimental blade models (Model1 and Model2). Model1 had lower stiffness in torsion so that the blade would not only bend but also twist passively by fluid forces and feather as the current speed was increasing. Model2 had higher stiffness in torsion so that the blade would bend without twisting deformation. We investigated the effects of the passive pitch control by comparing the behavior of both models. The material arrangement of Model1 is shown in Fig.4. A spar was made of unidirectional CFRP (CFRP-UD) in the longitudinal direction to suffer the bending load. In order to let the blade feather as the current speed is increasing, the spar is located along the leading edge (LE). Epoxy resin as core was filled to form the blade body and it was covered with a plain-woven CFRP (CFRP-cross) ply on the whole negative pressure side and the root of positive pressure side. Model2 was made of only CFRP-cross so that the torsion would be much smaller.

Fig.3. CAD model with dimensions of the 1m blade model.

Fig.4. Material arrangement of the Model1 (a view from positive pressure side).

2.3 Static Load Test

The static load tests were conducted to validate the FE model of the blade. Figure 5 shows the blade

model in the static load test. It was fixed at the root to be a cantilever. Load was applied to the tip in the corresponding direction to the current one so that the blade would bend and twist.

The FE model is shown in Fig.6 and the detail of a mesh is shown in Table 1. The parts of CFRP-UD and Epoxy were divided into solid elements. The division number is 86 (longitudinal direction), 20 (chord direction), and 2 (thickness direction). The solid elements had intermediate nodes. The part of CFRP-cross was divided into shell elements. The nodes at the root were fixed to be a cantilever and the load was applied at the tip. Table 2 shows the material property of CFRP-UD, CFRP-cross and Epoxy.

Table 3 shows the calculated and measured displacements of Model1 in the loading direction at both leading and trailing edges (LE and TE) of the position of $r/R = 0.7$. Table1 also shows twisting angles calculated from the difference of the displacement of LE and TE. The agreement between the calculated and measured results is good, but we can see that the experimental blade model is slightly stiffer than the FE model. This error might come from the difference of the thickness between the blade model and the FE model. Actually, the blade model was slightly thicker than the FE model.

Fig.5. Setup of static load test.

Fig.6. FE model.

Table1. Detail of the mesh division.

Node number		19773
Element number	Solid (hex20)	3440 (86 × 20 × 2)
	Shell (quad4)	2040

Table2. Material property of FE model (1: longitudinal direction 2: chord direction 3: thickness direction).

		CFRP-UD	CFRP-cross	Epoxy
Young's modulus	E ₁₁ [Gpa]	117	65	2.5
	E ₂₂ [Gpa]	7.6	65	
	E ₃₃ [Gpa]	7.6	9.5	
Longitudinal elastic modulus	G ₁₂ [Gpa]	3.5	3.5	1.2
	G ₂₃ [Gpa]	2.5	3.0	
	G ₃₁ [Gpa]	3.5	3.0	
Poisson ratio	NU ₁₂	0.0175	0.033	1.2
	NU ₂₃	0.43	0.057	
	NU ₃₁	0.27	0.39	

Table3. Results of the static load test and calculation.

	Displacement (mm)		Twisting angle (deg)
	LE	TE	
Calculation	1.85	3.47	2.01
Measurement	1.43	2.61	1.47

2.4 Deformation and Performance Evaluation during Rotation

We implemented the experiment in the towing tank to evaluate the deformation and performance of the composite blade models. Measurement system was developed as shown in Fig.7. In this system, 3D shape of objects was measured from the image captured by high speed stereo cameras. Measurement points were 0.3R, 0.5R, 0.7R 0.95R in radical position (R is a radius of the blade) and LE, 0.25C, 0.5C, 0.75C, TE in chord position (C is a chord length). We confirmed that measurement accuracy was 0.12 mm by a static and dynamic verification before the tank test [10]. Test conditions were $V=0.4, 0.6, 0.75$ m/s in current speed, and rotating speed was changed in a constant flow rate. The image of the towing tank test was showing in Fig.8.

The twisting angle and the amount of deflection were used as a barometer of deformation evaluation. The twisting angle, $\Delta\beta$, was determined based on the difference between the displacement of 0.25C and that of 0.75C as shown in Fig.9. The deflection indicates the deformation in the corresponding direction to the current one at the 0.25C in chord position, namely an aerodynamic center.

In FSIA, we used FLUENT (ANSYS Ltd.) as CFD software and ANSYS (ANSYS Ltd.) as FEA software. In the procedure of FSIA, firstly CFD calculation was carried out for the initial shape of the blades, and fluid forces on each CFD node were calculated. Secondly the nodal fluid forces were redistributed to FEA nodes. Thirdly the deformed shape was simulated by FEA calculation. In the FEA calculation, large deformation was conducted. These procedures were repeated until the results converge.

Figures 10 and 11 show the calculated and measured thrust. The agreement between calculated and measured results is good, but the result of calculation seems to be slightly higher than that of the experiment. In the case of Model1, the thrust decreases as the rotation speed increases because the blade caused torsional deformation and feathered.

The calculated and measured power coefficient in the condition of $V=0.75$ m/s are shown in Fig.12. The agreement between the calculated and measured results is good when rotation speed is low, but the large errors are observed when rotation speed is high. This result indicates the flow field couldn't be simulated strictly in CFD calculation.

Figure 13 shows the calculated and measured twisting angles of the position of $r/R = 0.7$ in the condition of $V=0.75$ m/s. In Model2 the experimental results are in accord with the calculated results. In Model1 some errors are observed, and the torsional deformation measured in the experiment is larger than the deformation simulated by FSIA.

The calculated and measured deflections are shown in Figs.14 and 15. The experimental results are similar to the calculated value. There are some errors between measurement and calculation. The trend of errors agrees with that of errors in the thrust.

Although we need further investigation to find the cause of errors, we confirmed that the experimental results were in good accord with calculated values. Consequently, we can conclude that deformation and performance evaluation of the passive pitch control

blade is possible by this combination of FSIA and water tank test.

Fig.7. Measurement system of the deformation of blade in towing tank.

Fig.8. Definition of twisting angle.

Fig.9. Towing tank test.

Fig.10. Measured and calculated results of thrust (Model1).

Fig.11. Measured and calculated results of thrust (Model2).

Fig.12. Measured and calculated results of power coefficient ($V=0.75$ m/s).

Fig.13. Measured and calculated results of twisting angle ($V=0.75$ m/s).

Fig.14. Measured and calculated results of deflection (Model1).

Fig.15. Measured and calculated results of deflection (Model2).

3 Conclusions

We proposed the passive pitch control system with a composite structure for a tidal current power generation. To evaluate the performance of a turbine blade deformed according to current and rotation speeds, we made the composite blade models and implemented FSIA and the towing tank test. We confirmed the agreement between the FE and manufactured models. Therefore we conclude that FSIA can be used to predict the deformation and performance of the blade model. We are designing the practical turbine and evaluating its performance based on FSIA.

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